

INSTILLING NATIONAL VALUES IN CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation. In the article, the upbringing of schoolchildren in the spirit of national values, on the basis of various didactic materials, was studied and analyzed scientifically and theoretically. Proposals and recommendations have been cited that highlight the place of national values in the upbringing of a child in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland.

Keywords: national value, song, fairy tale, proverb, national didactic materials.

The whole life of a person consists in the process of improving personal values, maturing self-esteem, striving to realize the value of others, Society, times and changes taking place from it. In order to realize the value of one's personality and others, a person's spiritual image and world, formed during his maturation, must serve goodness, have high social qualities, and he himself must be brought up to the point where he correctly understands the essence and purpose of life. In this sense, Socrates' "realize yourself!" the slogan is of great importance.

Today, it is one of the most important priorities for preschoolers to instill national values in their minds through education. It is our highest goal to shape the young people who build our future, realizing their identity, the great personalities who spread our nation and our self to the world on the basis of national values.

Today, serious work is being carried out in preschool educational organizations on the implementation of the concept prepared by 2030 of the improvement of the preschool education system approved by our President. Among them, there is a shortage of didactic materials aimed at educating schoolchildren in the spirit of national values. The fact that many of these materials are modernized materials prepared during the Soviet period, or Russian folk tales, proverbs and Pictures adapted to these values derived from these didactic materials aimed at educating preschoolers in the spirit of national values are much more relevant.

In the years of independence, an approach to this topic was formed in Uzbekistan on the basis of universal principles. The emergence of such a view, the social and spiritual renewal of values, the state-wide emphasis on the issues of maturation of members of society and their importance in youth education is the main direction of the development of this field. Values as one of the spiritual factors of strengthening independence, the positive processes in the field of aging necessitate an increase in research, a further increase in responsibility for them.

Independence has put on the agenda the re-establishment of issues and norms of Uzbek appreciation and improvement at the level of modern requirements in a unique eastern region formed over the centuries.

After all, the value system of a country that is not independent will never be shed. It is clear that in the spiritual life of a Colonial Country, the values of the colonists will be priority. Only independence will radically change this state, turning the country's set of values into an equal and truthful part of the world system. For this reason, independence also necessitated the formation of a new system of values. And this need is harmonized with the process of reevaluating values, the formation of a way of life, in which the criteria for Oriental, age-old and universal appreciation in our country are priority. This is also the reason why the need for attention to changes in the field of values and the use of new principles in this regard in education is increasing.

From ancient times, moral etiquette, respect for parents, respect for the teacher, loyalty to the motherland, loyalty to the ring, epics, fairy tales, songs, riddles, Proverbs, Proverbs, Proverbs, aphoristic phrases, Proverbs, myths, narration, anecdotes, in a word, examples of oral creativity are among them. In turn, this includes works on children's folklore, as well as samples with rich pages and color family upbringing, which are beautiful sages of ideological content and tolerance with badic features. Folkloric samples created by the people cannot be compared to any wealth, goods in the world. Each of them can be called an invaluable joke.

It is advisable if it is organized on the basis of various didactic materials in the upbringing of schoolchildren in preschool educational organizations in the spirit of national values. Let's cite the recommendations below in this regard:

The first didactic material deals with the theme of "Father-mind, mother-mind", and this didactic material is intended for a group of six-year-olds. Training takes place in the group room. Training takes 20 minutes. The training text is carried out in such forms as reading, statement, interaction, theatrical

appearance, recitation. Training is carried out on video and audio tools. In the process of training, breeders are rewarded with applause, toys.

Usually the educator calls the daily content and essence of this proverb the father padari buzrukvor, which is used many times, and the mother the loving mom. Because, for every person, there is no one who is great and dear to the father, kind and close to the mother. Indeed, parents are great ones. They will bring us into the world with you, preserve us like eyebrows, and not until adulthood, all the time the sun will shine light on our novelty life, and make our night Clear our light path, like a full moon. Therefore, it is not for nothing that the most beautiful epics, the best songs, the most pleasant melodies are dedicated to these great breeds. The above concepts are instilled in children in preschool educational organizations through songs, fairy tales, Proverbs, wise words.

In the people's affairs, the etiquette that follows it, it is emphasized that any child should be matured from an early age as a fighter in the interests of the el – yurt, and not himself, but as people who carry out the untenable dreams of generations of people thinking about happiness.

In preschool educational organizations, they are taught poetry and ghazals in instilling in them the concept of love, respect for children, parents, and their consciousness is developed. In the second didactic material, the educator on the topic “Motherland – Golden Cradle” initially explained that the people “Motherland – Golden Cradle” glorifies the motherland as such, instilling in its various case the use in the family, on the street, in kindergarten. Every old man of the motherland is holy and invites him to love, ardor. Indeed, the motherland is the Golden Cradle. We will come to the world in that's it Golden cradles, take the first step for the first time, grow up and come of age, tie ourselves to the service of el yurt. It is necessary to start worrying about the value of the Motherland, its maturation, flowering, tranquility from the very young age of the children. It is the sacred duty of every teacher to instill in any person the concepts of living the motherland proud of the Holy Land passed by their ancestors, constantly through educational upbringing.

In the process of educational upbringing, it is necessary to form feelings for each child, such as love for the motherland – to work honestly on the path of prosperity of the motherland, to prepare oneself for the sacraments. It is necessary to honor the land in which he lives, preserve nature and elegance, add beauty to his beauty, be able to love people, read excellently, behave hush, be brought up as a hush Image.

In conclusion, we should educate the future generation in preschool educational organizations in the spirit of respect for parents on the basis of national values, respect for the teacher, loyalty to the people, unlimited love for the motherland.

In this regard, it is in accordance with the proverb that these values are instilled in the minds of children by organizing spiritual and educational activities in every activity in preschool educational organizations, through Proverbs, fairy tales, poems from folk oral creativity.

It is extremely important to teach preschoolers the basics of modern value science, which is a complex of knowledge about the feeling of value and appreciation, the category of values, their essence, content, images of manifestation in the education and formation of spiritual perfect generations. For this reason, the generalized areas of knowledge of the achievements of the universal in relation to the standards of retribution, the use of opportunity is one of the main criteria for the effectiveness of Education.

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